

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH AND BIO-SCIENCE

BIOANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF QUININE AND CIPROFLOXACIN BY USING RP-HPLC

RAMESH L. SAWANT, KALYANI A. JADHAV, KALLYANI D. TANPURE, ANJALI V. BHARAT

Padmashri Dr. Vithalrao Vikhe Patil Foundation's College of Pharmacy, Ahmednagar, (MS), India, 414111

Accepted Date: 29/05/2015; Published Date: 27/08/2015

Abstract: A new, rapid, sensitive and specific liquid chromatographic method with UV detection for the simultaneous estimation of quinine and ciprofloxacin was developed. Separation was achieved with Hibar^R 250-4.6 HPLC column Purosphens^R STAR RP-18 and mobile phase containing acetonitrile: methanol: triethylamine (0.1%) in double grade distilled water in the ratio 1:6:3 (pH was adjusted with ortho-phosphoric acid as 3.8) at flow rate 1 ml/min. containing biological matrix as animal plasma with the addition of anticoagulant EDTA. Micro-centrifuge (Romi, RM-12C.) was used for the preparation of biological matrix. Quantitation was achieved with UV detector at 236 nm. The selected chromatographic conditions effectively separated quinine and ciprofloxacin with retention time of 3.092 and 4.158 min. respectively. The developed method is precise, accurate, reproducible and specific.

Keywords: Biological matrix, Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride, Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography, Quinine Sulphate.

PAPER-QR CODE

Corresponding Author: MS. KALYANI A. JADHAV

Access Online On:

www.ijprbs.com

How to Cite This Article:

Kalyani A. Jadhav, IJPRBS, 2015; Volume 4(4): 36-47

INTRODUCTION

Quinine sulphate is a white or almost white, needle like crystals or crystalline powder. It is slightly soluble in water, sparingly soluble in boiling water and in alcohol, completely soluble in acetonitrile. The pH of a 10 g/l suspension in water is 5.7 to 6.6. Store in air tight containers, protected from light.

1.1. Drug Profile:

Cinchonan-9-ol, 6'-methoxy-(8 α , 9R)-sulphate (2:1) (salt), dihydrate

1.1.1. Chemical structure:

Fig.1. Structure of quinine sulphate

1.1.2. Molecular formula:

$(C_{20}H_{24}N_2O_2) \cdot 2H_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$

1.1.3. Molecular weight:

782.96 g/mol^[1]

1.1.4. Mechanism of action:

Quinine is cinchona alkaloid that acts as a blood schizonticidal and weak gametocyte against *plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium malariae*. As an alkaloid it is accumulated in the blood vacuoles of plasmodium species. Quinine is less effective and more toxic as a blood schizonticidal agent than chloroquine. However still it is very effective and widely used in the treatment of acute cases of severe *P. falciparum*. It is especially useful in the areas where there is known to be a high level of resistance to chloroquine^[2].

1.1.5. Drug interactions:

Acenocoumarol- Quinine, a moderate CYP2C9 inhibitor, may increase the serum concentration of acenocoumarol by decreasing its metabolism via CYP2C9.

Anisindione- Quinine may increase the anticoagulant effect of anisindione.

Artemether- Quinine may increase the adverse effects of artemether. Combination therapy is contraindicated unless there are no other treatment options.

Digitoxin- Quinine/quinidine increases the effect of digoxin.

Metocurine- The quinine derivative increases the effect of the muscle relaxant.

Terfenadine- Increased risk of cardiotoxicity and arrhythmias ^[3].

1.1.6. Uses:

Quinine is cinchona alkaloid that acts as a blood schizonticidal and weak gametocyte against *plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium malariae*. As an alkaloid it is accumulated in the blood vacuoles of plasmodium species. Quinine is less effective and more toxic as a blood schizonticidal agent than chloroquine. However still it is very effective and widely used in the treatment of acute cases of severe *P. falciparum*. It is especially useful in the areas where there is known to be a high level of resistance to chloroquine ^[4].

Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride is a pale yellow, slightly hygroscopic, crystalline powder. It is soluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol, very slightly soluble in ethanol, practically insoluble in acetone, in ethyl acetate, and in methylene chloride. A solution has pH 3.5 to 4.5. Store in an air tight container, protected from light.

1.2. Drug Profile:

1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinolinecarboxylic acid hydrochloride monohydrate

1.2.1. Chemical structure:

Fig.2. Structure of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride

1.2.2. Molecular formula:

$C_{17}H_{18}FN_3O_3 \cdot HCl \cdot H_2O$

1.2.3. Molecular weight:

385.8 g/mol^[5]

1.2.4. . Mechanism of action:

Ciprofloxacin has *in-vitro* activity against a wide range of gram-negative and gram-positive microorganisms. The bactericidal action of ciprofloxacin results from inhibition of the enzymes topoisomerase II (DNA gyrase) and topoisomerase IV, which are required for bacterial DNA replication, transcription, repair and recombination^[6].

1.2.5. Drug interactions:

Clozapine- Ciprofloxacin may increase clozapine serum levels.

Cyclosporine- Ciprofloxacin may increase the effect and toxicity of cyclosporine.

Lomitapide- The effect of coadministration of lomipatide with ciprofloxacin, and other moderate CYP3A4 inhibitors (such as aprepitant, amprenavir, atazanavir, ciprofloxacin, crizotinib, darunavir/ritonavir, diltiazem, erythromycin, fluconazole, fosamprenavir, imatinib, verapamil) is unknown. However, as coadministration is likely to increase serum concentrations of lomipatide, concomitant use is contraindicated.

Theophylline- Ciprofloxacin may increase the effect of theophylline^[7].

1.2.6. Uses:

Ciprofloxacin has *in-vitro* activity against a wide range of gram-negative and gram-positive microorganisms. The bactericidal action of ciprofloxacin results from inhibition of the enzymes topoisomerase II (DNA gyrase) and topoisomerase IV, which are required for bacterial DNA replication, transcription, repair and recombination^[8-9].

Quinine and ciprofloxacin both drugs are used for the treatment of malaria and typhoid fever respectively. There are so many methods described for the quinine and ciprofloxacin but there is no method estimated for RP-HPLC for both the drugs individually.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Chemicals and Reagents:

Acetonitrile (HPLC grade), double distilled water, methanol (HPLC grade) was obtained from S. D. fine-chem. limited, worli Mumbai. Triethylamine (AR grade) was obtained from S. D. fine-chem. limited, worli Mumbai. Animal plasma obtained from delta laboratories, Bangalore, Ortho-phosphoric acid (85% pure) was obtained from Merck specialties private limited, worli, Mumbai.

2.2. Biological matrix:

Animal plasma with Ethylene Di-amine Tetra Acetic acid (EDTA) as an anticoagulant was used as a biological matrix during method validation.

2.3. Instrumentation:

A Jasco LC-Net-II/ADC with intelligent UV/VIS detector (UV-2075 plus), intelligent HPLC pump (PU-2080 Plus) and RP-C18 column (Purospher^R STAR) was used. Micro-centrifuge (Romi, RM-12C.) was used for preparation of biological sample. A manual syringe injector was used for the injection of sample. The HPLC system was equipped with Borwin software for data processing.

2.4. Determination of appropriate UV wavelength:

The appropriate wavelength for the detection of the drug in mobile phase was determined by wavelength scanning over the range of 200-400 nm. After scanning appropriate wavelength was selected.

2.5. Preparation of mobile phase:

The mobile phase was prepared using acetonitrile: methanol: 0.1% triethylamine in water: (1:6:3), pH of which was adjusted to 3.8 with ortho-phosphoric acid was found to resolve quinine and ciprofloxacin. The degassing of mobile phase was done by sonication for 60 min. The flow rate was set to 1.0 ml/min. Both drugs showed good absorbance at 235 nm, which was selected as wavelength for further analysis. The column temperature was maintained at room temperature.

2.6. Preparation of biological matrix:

2.6.1. Preparation of animal plasma by centrifugation:

Animal blood was collected. The fresh blood were taken and added to the Ethylene di-amine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) as an anticoagulant was used as a biological matrix. The centrifugation

process was used for the separation of plasma from the blood. It was centrifuge for 10 min with 3000 rpm by using micro-centrifuge. Then the plasma was ready for the preparation of sample.

2.6.2. Preparation of sample solution:

The animal plasma was taken for the preparation of sample. The drug weight 1 mg of each quinine and ciprofloxacin and added to the 5 ml of plasma. Again it was centrifuge for 10 min. (3000 r.p.m.). The sample solution was ready for sample injection.

2.7. Chromatographic Condition:

The mobile phase was prepared using acetonitrile: methanol: 0.1% triethylamine in water: (1:6:3), pH of which was adjusted to 3.8 with ortho-phosphoric acid was found to resolve quinine and ciprofloxacin. The degassing of mobile phase was done by sonication for 60 min. The flow rate was set to 1.0 ml/min. Both drugs showed good absorbance at 235 nm, which was selected as wavelength for further analysis. The column temperature was maintained at room temperature.

2.8. Preparation of Stock Solutions:

Standard stock solutions containing quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride were prepared individually by dissolving 1 mg of drug in 10 ml volumetric flask using mobile phase with biological matrix and volume is make up to the mark. This will give 100 µg/ml of solution respectively for both drugs and used for sample injection.

2.9. Retention time (tR):

Retention time (tR) is the time it takes a solute to travel through the column. The retention time is assigned to the corresponding solute peak. The retention time is a measure of the amount of time a solute spends in a column. It is the sum of the time spent in the stationary phase and the mobile phase⁽⁹⁾.

2.10. Resolution factor (R):

Resolution factor shows the accuracy of the quantitative analysis and resolution factor should be greater than 1.5 or specified in the individual monograph.

Resolution factor can be calculated by the formula:

$$R = 2 (t_2 - t_1) / 2.70 (W_{1h/2} + W_{2h/2}),$$

Where, W= Peak width, h= Height, t₁= Retention time of first peak, t₂= Retention time of second peak.

2.11. Tailing factor (T):

It should meet the requirements of the individual monograph and can be calculated by the formula:

$T = W_{0.05} / 2F$, Where, $W_{0.05}$ = Peak width at 5 % high, F = Leading edge of peak ^[10].

2.12. Capacity factor (k'):

The capacity factor (also called "capacity ratio") is symbolized by k' (USP terminology) or k (IUPAC/ASTM terminology). It is a measure of the retention of a peak that is independent of column geometry or mobile phase flow rate. The capacity factor is calculated as: $k' = (t_R - t_0) / t_0$. Where t_R is the retention time of the peak, and t_0 is the dead time of the column ^[11].

2.13. Asymmetry factor:

The asymmetry factor is a measure of peak tailing. It is defined as the distance from the center line of the peak to the back slope divided by the distance from the center line of the peak to the front slope, with all measurements made at 10 % of the maximum peak height. The asymmetry factor of a peak will typically be similar to the tailing factor for the same peak, but the two values cannot be directly converted ^[12].

2.14. Theoretical plates:

Theoretical plate represents the column efficiency. It should meet the value given in the monograph. It can be calculated by the following formula:

$N_a = N_t / E$, Where, N_a = is the number of actual, physical plates or trays, N_t is the number of theoretical plates or trays and E is the plate or tray efficiency ^[13].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Wavelength selection:

The ultraviolet spectra of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride showed at 233 nm and 272 nm respectively. Therefore, 236 nm was wavelength selected to achieve the highest sensitivity for the study.

3.2. Selection of mobile phase:

Different combinations of acetonitrile, methanol and water with 0.1 % triethylamine with pH adjusted to 3.8 by using ortho-phosphoric acid were tested and the optimum condition at acetonitrile: methanol: 0.1% triethylamine in water (1:6:3 v/v/v) containing biological matrix.

The obtained chromatograph showed a retention time for quinine sulphate 3.092 (Figure 5 and Table 1) and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride 4.158 (Figure 6 and Table 2) respectively. In the synthetic mixture of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride shows rapid separation with retention time 3.092 and 4.158 respectively (Figure 7 and Table 3).

A bio analytical method development by using rp-hplc method for the simultaneous estimation of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride was developed. The peaks of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride are found to be well separated at 3.092 and 4.158 respectively using acetonitrile: methanol: 0.1% triethylamine in water (1:6:3 v/v/v) P^H of which was adjusted to 3.8 with ortho-phosphoric acid as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min with wavelength set to 236 nm containing animal plasma.

3.3. Selection of HPLC stationary phase:

The best results were obtained by using Hibar^R 250-4.6 HPLC column Purosphens^R STAR RP-18 as compared to other different stationary phase.

Fig.3. Spectra of quinine sulphate in distilled water

Fig.4. Spectra of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in distilled water.

3.4. Separation of quinine sulphate by using biological matrix:

The sample preparation was done by taking 1 mg of quinine sulphate and added to the 5 ml of plasma containing anticoagulant and centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 min. And apply as an injection to HPLC.

Fig.No.5. Chromatogram of quinine sulphate sample in biological matrix at λ_{max} (236 nm).

Table.No.1. Chromatographic data for quinine sulphate in biological matrix:

Name	R.T. (min.)	Area [$\mu V \cdot Sec$]	Resolution	Plates	Asymmetry	Capacity
Qui. Sulpha.	3.092	3544350.223	1.53	1184.40	2.38	370.00

Total Area of Peak = 3544350.223 [$\mu V \cdot Sec$]

3.5. Separation of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride by using biological matrix:

The sample preparation was done by taking 1 mg of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and added to the 5 ml of plasma containing anticoagulant and centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 min. And apply as an injection to HPLC.

Fig.No.6. Chromatogram of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride sample in biological matrix at λ_{max} (236 nm).

Table No.2. Chromatographic data for ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in biological matrix:

Name	R.T. (min.)	Area [μ V.Sec]	Resolution	Plates	Asymmetry	Capacity
Cipro. Hydro.	4.158	1696294.590	1.61	1305.92	1.91	498.00

Total Area of Peak =1696294.590 [μ V.Sec]

3.6. Separation of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride by using biological matrix as synthetic mixture:

The sample preparation was done by taking 1 mg of each quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride and added as a synthetic mixture to the 5 ml of plasma containing anticoagulant and centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 min. and apply as an injection to HPLC.

Fig.No.7. Chromatogram of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride synthetic mixture in biological matrix at λ_{max} (236 nm).

TableNo.3. Chromatographic data for quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in biological matrix as synthetic mixture:

Name	R.T. (min.)	Area [μ V.Sec]	Resolution	Plates	Asymmetry	Capacity
Qui. Sulpha.	3.092	3544350.223	1.53	1184.40	2.38	370.00
Cipro. Hydro.	4.158	1696294.590	1.61	1305.92	1.91	498.00

4. CONCLUSION:

The developed bio analytical method by using rp-hplc method is novel, accurate, sensitive, unique, precise, eco friendly, cost effective, fast and reproducible for simultaneous estimation of quinine sulphate and ciprofloxacin hydrochloride in bulk mixture. The method utilizes simple sample preparation, short analysis time and elution is done by isocratic method. It is concluded that this method can be adopted by the industries and academic institutions for their combination drug estimation. It shows novelty and utility of the overall work.

5. REFERENCES:

1. Indian Pharmacopoeia, Government of India Ministry of Health And Family Welfare, Published by The Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, GAZIABAD, Volume III, 2010; 1092-1093.
2. Vugt M, Brockman A, Gemperli B, Luxemburger C, Gathmann I, Royce C, Slight T, Looareesuwan S, White N J, Nosten F., A randomised comparison of artemether-benflumetol and artesunate-mefloquine in the treatment of multidrug resistant falciparum malaria. Antimicrobe Agents Chemother, 1998; 42:135-139.
3. Quinine-Wikipedia (<http://www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB00468#drug-interactions>) Accessed 1 May 2015.
4. Indian Pharmacopoeia, Government of India Ministry of Health And Family Welfare, Published by The Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, GAZIABAD, Volume III, 2010; 2025-2026.
5. National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards, Methods for Dilution Antimicrobial Susceptibility Tests for Bacteria That Grow Aerobically-5th Edition, Approved Standard NCCLS Document M7-A5, 2000;20, No.2, NCCLS, Wayne, PA and January.
6. Ciprofloxacin- Wikipedia (<http://www.rxlist.com/proquin-xr-drug/clinical-pharmacology.htm>) Accessed 1 May 2015.
7. Ciprofloxacin- Wikipedia (<http://www.drugbank.ca/drugs/DB00468#drug-interactions>) Accessed 1 May 2015.
8. National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards, Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Disk Susceptibility Tests-7th Edition, Approved Standard NCCLS Document M2-A7, 2000; 20, No.1, NCCLS, Wayne, PA and January.
9. Terms and Definitions – Agilent Technologies, (www.chem.agilent.com/cag/cabu/terms&def.htm).

10. Resolution factor, tailing factor, theoretical plates
(www.pharmaguideline.com/2011/09/resolution-factor-telling-factor.html) Accessed 1 May 2015.

11. Capacity factor – Wikipedia Lc sources,
(www.lcresources.com/resources/TSWiz/hs210.htm) Accessed 1 May 2015.

12. Asymmetry factor Lc sources, Wikipedia
(www.lcresources.com/resources/TSWiz/hs170.htm) Accessed 1 May 2015.

13. Theoretical plates- Wikipedia (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theoretical_plate) Accessed 1 May 2015.